

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Identifying entrepreneurial discovery processes with weak and strong technology signals: a text mining approach

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Abstract

This study aims to propose methods for identifying entrepreneurial discovery processes with weak/strong signals of technological changes and incorporating technology foresight in the design and planning of the Smart Specialization Strategy (S3). For this purpose, we first analyse patent abstracts from 2000 to 2009, obtained from the European Patent Office and use a keyword-based text mining approach to collect weak and strong technology signals; the word2vec algorithm is also employed to group weak signal keywords. We then utilize Correlation Explanation (CorEx) topic modelling to link technology weak/strong signals to invention activities for the period 2010-2018 and use the ANOVA statistical method to examine the relationship between technology weak/strong signals and patent values. The results suggest that patents related to weak rather than strong signals are more likely to be high-impact innovations and to serve as a basis for future technological developments. Furthermore, we use latent Dirichlet allocation (LDA) topic modelling to analyse patent activities related to weak/strong technology signals and compute regional topic weights. Finally, we present implications of the research.

Keywords

Smart Specialization Strategy (S3), Entrepreneurial Discovery Process (EDP), technology foresight, weak signals, innovations, patents, text mining, topic modelling, word2vec.

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Plain language summary

The European Union (EU) has introduced Smart Specialization Strategy (S3) to increase the innovation and competitive potential of its regions by encouraging them to specialize in limited key economic areas. However, as the quantity of information is growing rapidly in today's digital economy, regional policy-makers lack efficient and viable tools to interpret external information, knowledge and map promising areas for smart specialization. To address this issue, we used text mining methods to identify entrepreneurial discovery processes with weak/strong signals of technological changes and incorporate technology foresight in the design and planning of S3. For this purpose, we first analysed patent abstracts from 2000 to 2009 provided by European Patent Office and used a keyword-based text mining approach to collect technology weak and strong signals. We then linked technology weak/strong signals to invention activities for the period 2010–2018 and examine the relationship between technology weak/strong signals and patent values. The results suggest that patents related to weak rather than strong signals are more likely to be high-impact innovations and to serve as a basis for future technological developments. Furthermore, we used topic modelling to analyse patent activities related to weak/strong technology signals and compute regional topic weights.

Introduction

The European Union (EU) has introduced the [Smart Specialization Strategy](#) (S3) to promote sustainable and inclusive economic growth in its regions by inducing them to discover and develop economic areas in which they can have comparative and competitive advantage. S3 is a place-based and bottom-up innovation policy which allows the EU regions to tap into their endogenous potential ([Coffano & Foray, 2014](#); [Foray et al., 2009](#)). As knowledge and competencies are dispersed and divided locally, “entrepreneurs in the broadest sense (innovative firms, research leaders in higher education institutions, independent inventors and innovators) are in the best position to discover the domains of R&D and innovation in which a region is likely to excel given its existing capabilities and productive assets” ([Foray & Goenaga, 2013](#)). For this reason, S3 relies on an entrepreneurial discovery process (EDP) to map promising areas for investment and specialization ([Coffano & Foray, 2014](#)). The role of regional governments in S3 is to identify potential entrepreneurial discovery projects and to develop critical mass in these strategic priority areas in order to facilitate micro-level discovery and experimentation processes ([Foray et al., 2011](#)), but policymakers lack appropriate tools and methods to identify and assess promising EDPs.

Previous research studies the distribution of knowledge claims by regional patents and explores co-occurrence of technology classes to identify industry diversification and specialization opportunities across EU regions ([Balland et al., 2019](#); [Montresor & Quatraro, 2020](#)). Another strand of literature utilizes an unsupervised text mining approach to explore latent topics and to map innovation ecosystems based on start-up activities and scientific publications ([Bzhalava et al., 2018](#); [Moilanen et al., 2021](#)). Although the prior research provides valuable insights for

understanding specialization patterns across regions, we lack an understanding of how to identify and assess EDPs based on technology weak signals. Weak signals are defined “as seemingly random or disconnected pieces of information that at first appear to be background noise, but which can be recognized as part of a larger pattern when viewed through a different frame or by connecting it with other pieces of information” ([Schoemaker et al., 2013](#)). In other words, they are the early signs for future disruptions and discontinuities and being able to monitor and analyse weak signals can help decision-makers substantially in predicting impending technological and business changes. Hence, incorporating weak signal technology in studying and evaluating entrepreneurial discovery processes can help regional governments to map promising areas of future specialization across territories and to design European S3 ([Paliokaitė et al., 2015](#); [Paliokaitė et al., 2016](#)).

Theoretical framework

By adopting S3, EU aims to avoid duplication and fragmentation of its resources and to increase effectiveness of its research and innovation activities in the face of increased global competition ([Foray et al., 2011](#); [McCann & Ortega-Argilés, 2016](#)). In contrast to traditional industrial and innovation policy in which a decision-making process was mainly centralized and top-down, S3 is a bottom-up collective reflection process in which local actors from industry and academia discover technology and market opportunities and identify promising areas for specialization ([Coffano & Foray, 2014](#)). As knowledge are fragmented and distributed among local actors and setting innovation-policy priorities involve many uncertainties, policymakers usually lack sufficient information to identify future growth opportunities. For this reason, traditional industrial policy and its top-down approach in setting innovation priorities often failed to promote local economic development ([Barca et al., 2012](#); [McCann & Ortega-Argilés, 2016](#)). In particular, “the evidence from numerous development policy examples worldwide demonstrates that regions have made many mistakes in terms of their policy choices, and often this was because policies were chosen on the basis of criteria which were not appropriate or relevant for the local context” ([McCann & Ortega-Argilés, 2016](#)). As old industrial policy relies ‘one-size-fits-all’ strategy solutions and advocates the replication of successful innovation policies applied in very different contexts, it was ineffective to stimulate endogenous economic potential across regions and often caused underdevelopment ([Barca et al., 2012](#); [McCann & Ortega-Argilés, 2016](#)). Moreover, traditional innovation and development policies mainly focus on securing continuity of technology and industrial structure, and for this reason, it placed great emphasis on interests of large established firms in setting innovation priorities ([Asheim, 2019](#)). As incumbent firms mainly rely on the dominant design in their production system and concentrate on generating incremental innovations through exploiting mature technologies and existing knowledge ([Lindholm-Dahlstrand et al., 2019](#)), the traditional industrial policy constrains local innovation activities ([Asheim, 2019](#); [Isaksen & Trippl, 2016](#)). In contrast, S3 focuses on altering and renewing of technology and industrial structures across territories and relies on EDP in identifying future growth opportunities

(Foray, 2015). EDP is an inclusive process and involves a wide range of local agents from business and academia to discover and produce information about new activities of future specialization, whereas ‘the regional government assesses the activities’ potential and empowers those actors most capable of realizing that potential’ (Virkkala & Mariussen, 2018). Hence, entrepreneurs (in the broadest sense) explore new market opportunities and bring into existence novel ideas and technologies as well as reshape markets and value networks across industries (Lindholm-Dahlstrand *et al.*, 2019; Schumpeter, 1934). This process is termed as “creative destruction” in the classic innovation literature (Schumpeter, 1934). In “creative destruction” process entrepreneurial firms bring new technologies to the market and out-compete established companies by cannibalizing their market profit (which based on existing technologies) and making the value of their accumulated knowledge obsolete. This, in turn, leads shifting profit pools from incumbents to new firms, as well as rearranging industry structures and replacing established businesses (Lindholm-Dahlstrand *et al.*, 2019). Hence, by relying on EDP, European S3 aims to implement structural economic changes across regions through identifying new domains of future opportunities in which they can have competitive advantages and concentrating resources on those key limited areas (Foray, 2015).

To examine regional knowledge bases and to identify technological upgrading (diversification) opportunities, previous research uses co-occurrence analysis and explores patent technology classes in regional patent databases (Balland *et al.*, 2019; Montresor & Quatraro, 2020), as well as studies trademark business classifications to detect future growth opportunities across European regions (Drivas, 2020). In contrast, Moilanen *et al.* (2021) employ an unsupervised text mining method to detect latent topics and thematic networks in scientific literature. Other strand of literature utilizes network analysis to examine startup company sub-industry tags and business descriptions to explore the structure of entrepreneurial ecosystems and to examine where entrepreneurs drive their businesses across different sectors and territories and to detect specialization patterns (Basole *et al.*, 2018; Losurdo *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, Papagiannidis *et al.* (2018) use an unsupervised text mining approach to discover latent topics in websites of firms and visually identify areas of intense business activities across various places. Similarly, other scholars explore web pages of firms to map innovation ecosystems (Beaudry *et al.*, 2016; Kinne & Axenbeck, 2020). In particular, as web pages of companies are often used to publish information about innovative products/services, previous research uses web and text mining methods to survey business websites and to detect innovation activities across territories (Beaudry *et al.*, 2016; Kinne & Axenbeck, 2020).

To understand future technology and market landscape and to identify promising EDPs, foresight can be significantly helpful as an instrument to study the potential ways in which the future technology and market landscape can unfold. Specifically, foresight is defined ‘as a process which involves systematic inquiry into longer-term futures, including emerging and novel issues, which in turn enables present decision-making and action’ (Minkinen *et al.*, 2019). In the process of strategic planning

with foresight, a well-known approach is to identify and analyze weak signals which are the early signs of future disruptions and discontinuities (Thorleuchter & Van den Poel, 2015). To process massive amounts of information and to analyze technology/business related weak signals, prior studies propose text mining methods (Kim & Lee, 2017; Thorleuchter & Van den Poel, 2013; Thorleuchter & Van den Poel, 2015; Yoon, 2012). In particular, Yoon (2012) develop a keyword-based weak signal detection approach to assess the strength of the terms for each topic by measuring keyword frequency (visibility) and the degree of diffusion-based on document frequency, as well as calculates time-weighted increasing rates of keywords based on their degree of visibility/diffusion and computes average term (document) frequency to identify weak and strong signal related terms. Similarly, Kim & Lee (2017) propose the novelty-focused weak signal detection approach by first applying text mining to extract signals from documents and then employing a local outlier factor to study the rarity and paradigm unrelatedness of weak signals. Although prior research develops big data and text mining tools to identify weak signals of impending technological and business changes, we lack an understanding of how to incorporate technology foresight in the design and planning of European S3. To study this issue, the research aims to identify and assess EDPs (e.g. invention activities) with technology weak and strong signals. It is important to apply Big Data analytics to understand EDPs.

Methods

In this research, we used patent claim data from the European Patent Office (EPO). EPO provides access all European Patent (EP) publications from 1978 until the end of January 2019. EP publications are in XML, PDF and TIFF formats and this makes it difficult to extract only publication text data. To address this issue, EPO created EP full-text data for text analytics and provides free and easy access to EP publication text data, which includes information about the publication authority, number, publication kind, date, the language of text component, text type (i.e. title, abstract, description of the invention, a set of claims) as well as the publication abstract and the full-text description of the invention. As a patent abstract text includes essential information about an invention and its technical details (Lee *et al.*, 2019), we used patent claim abstract data in our research and extracted only abstracts with English language from EP full-text data (for further details, see *Underlying data*). In the study, we aim to identify invention activities associated with weak/strong signals of technological changes and to incorporate technology foresight in the design and planning of S3. For this purpose, in line with previous research, we first collected weak/strong technology signals from patents abstracts during ten years period from 2000 to 2009 (Kwon *et al.*, 2018; Yoon, 2012), and then we linked weak/strong technology signals with invention activities during 2010-2018 time period.

To identify regional dimension of patent abstracts (for 2010 to 2018) and to measure their quality, we combined EP data with the OECD-REGPAT and OECD Patent Quality Indicators databases by using the patent publication number. The OECD-REGPAT database January 2020 allows to connect patent data with regional dimension by using the addresses of the applicants

and inventors. The OECD Patent Quality Indicators database July 2020 provides information about indicators of patent technological and economic values (e.g. number of citations a patent received up to five years after publication, and if a patent belongs to the top 1% highly cited patents up to five years after publication).

Identifying weak signals with keyword-based text mining

We then cleaned and pre-processed patent abstracts, which involved transforming all textual content into lower case keywords and deleting numbers, non-English and special characters, as well as removing punctuations and stop-words. Moreover, keywords are lemmatized, which refers to applying vocabulary and morphological analysis and transforming keywords into their root forms. We then extracted only noun and adjective keywords as they represent technology concepts and, in line with Yoon (2012), we calculated their Degree of Visibility (DoV) based on the frequency of their occurrence and Degree of Diffusion (DoD) based on their appearance in number of patent abstracts. Mathematically, DoV and DoD are expressed in the following way:

$$DoV_{ij} = \left(\frac{TF_{ij}}{NN_{ij}} \right) \times \{1 - tw \times (n - j)\} \quad (1)$$

$$DoD_{ij} = \left(\frac{DF_{ij}}{NN_{ij}} \right) \times \{1 - tw \times (n - j)\} \quad (2)$$

where TF_{ij} refers to the total occurrence frequency of a term i in period j , and DF_{ij} denotes to the document frequency of term i in period j . NN_{ij} stands for the total number of patent abstracts in period j , whereas n is the number of periods. Furthermore, to put more weight on recent appearances of keywords and to give recent occurrences of keywords more importance than past occurrences, Yoon (2012) introduces tw (a time-weight) which is defined as 0.05. Moreover, the geometric mean is calculated based on DoV and DoD values to explore the increasing rates of keyword occurrences. Terms associated with weak signal topics usually have a low absolute occurrence frequency and a high time-weighted increasing rates. On the contrary, terms related to strong signal topics are likely to have a high absolute occurrence frequency and a high time-weighted increasing rates. In line with Yoon (2012), we extract keywords that are in the top 30% in terms of growth rate. Finally, we consider keywords that have less than average absolute yearly term (document) frequency as weak signals, and those with more than average absolute yearly term (document) frequency as strong signals.

By analyzing patent abstract data for the period 2000–2009, we identified weak and strong signal keywords related to hospitality/travel, education, telecommunication, healthcare, media and entertainment, environment, transportation and construction industries. Specifically, the following weak signal keywords were identified for the hospitality/travel industry: cooking, accommodation, wine, leisure. For the education industry – education; for the telecommunication industry – cell

phone; for the healthcare industry – care, health, vaccine, symptom, anticancer. For the media and entertainment industry – advertisement, media, gaming; for the environment technologies/industries – planet, biosensor, biomass, greenhouse, sustainability; for the transportation industry – motorcycle, flight; for the construction industry – cement, construct. Afterwards, we utilised the word2vec algorithm to group weak signal keywords (Mikolov *et al.*, 2013). In particular, we first kept only weak signal keywords in patent abstracts and removed other words. We then utilised word2vec to train text corpus and extract terms that have high correlation (0.70–0.99 range) with the industry keywords; the word2vec algorithm uses a neural network approach to create word embeddings by learning word associations (co-occurrence) from text and locating words with similar meaning close to one another in the vector space (Mikolov *et al.*, 2013). Strong signal keywords were also classified into telecommunication, healthcare, media and entertainment, environment and transportation sectors. For weak and strong signal keywords and their total frequencies, as well as their Degree of Visibility (DoV) and Degree of Diffusion (DoD) values, see *Extended data* (Bzhalava *et al.*, 2022b).

Linking weak/strong signals to patent abstracts

After collecting weak and strong signal related keywords, we linked them with EU patent abstract data for the period 2010–2018. For this purpose, we first cleaned and pre-processed textual context of patent abstracts and then utilised Correlation Explanation (CorEx) topic modelling, which is a semi-supervised text mining approach that allows the defining of “anchor words” and guides learning topics in the direction of those anchor words (Gallagher *et al.*, 2017). In other words, we use weak and strong signal keywords as anchor words and use CorEx topic modelling to identify related invention activities across EU regions for the period 2010–2018. In total, we identify 366,392 patents associated with weak and strong signals. Moreover, we apply latent Dirichlet allocation (LDA) to discover hidden topics in those patent abstracts. LDA is an unsupervised machine learning method which automatically creates cluster terms that have a higher possibility of showing up together and reveals latent topics in a collection of documents (Blei *et al.*, 2003). To decide the number of topics to search in patent abstracts and to measure the quality of the topics discovered, we tested a range of topic numbers from 2 to 50 and calculated coherence scores (ibid). Finally, we selected topics with the highest coherence score and ran LDA with 7 topics.

Furthermore, we employed a one-way ANOVA modelling to study the relationship between weak/strong signals and patent values. Patent quality is usually measured by the number of forward citations it receives (Briggs & Buehler, 2018; Hall *et al.*, 2005). A patent is considered as breakthrough if it receives a disproportionately large number of forward citations and has a considerably large impact on subsequent technological progress (Arts & Veugelers, 2015; Squicciarini *et al.*, 2013). In line of prior research, we measured a patent quality by (1) number of citations it receives up to five years after publication and also (2) if it belongs to the top 1% highly cited patents up to

five years after publication. The first one is a continuous variable, whereas the second one is a binary variable - 1 if a patent is classified as a breakthrough and 0 otherwise (Squicciarini *et al.*, 2013).

Results

The results show that major invention activities related to weak signals of technological changes are concentrated in sustainability, anticancer, symptom, vaccine and greenhouse areas, whereas patent activities associated with strong signal keywords are concentrated in mobile technologies, healthcare and aircraft/vehicle areas (see Table 1–Table 2). Moreover, we also examined whether patents associated with weak or strong signals have more technological and economic values in terms of number of citations a patent received up to 5 years after publication, and if a patent belongs to the top 1% highly cited patents up to 5 years after publication. By employing the one-way ANOVA modelling approach, the results suggest that patents related to technology weak rather than strong signals are more likely to be high-impact innovations and to serve as a basis for future technological developments (see Table 3–Table 6). Technology foresight can provide vital input in the design and planning of European S3 in terms of providing information about emerging technologies, discontinuities and potential future threats and opportunities.

focused on the most frequent words that are important to interpret and distinguish topics. Looking at the results of LDA topic modelling, Table 7 shows that major invention activities associated with water technologies (Topic 0), cell domain/embodiment (Topic 1), image display (Topic 2), protein acid (Topic 3), data systems (Topic 4), sensor-based intelligence systems (Topic 5) and aircraft/vehicle power systems (Topic 6). Moreover, we investigated the prevalence of each topic by calculating region topic proportions. By assuming that documents are a probability distribution of topics and topics are a probability distribution of words, LDA calculates probability distributions that a document (in our case a patent abstract) is associated with multiple topics. Hence, LDA allows us to present documents with corresponding topic probabilities and to show how different topics are distributed over patent abstracts as well as to calculate regional patent weights. After LDA analysis, we obtained probability vectors over topics for each patent abstract. We sum topic probabilities of patent abstracts in each EU regions to study which European regions in which areas/topics contribute invention activities.

The top EU regions with the highest probability distributions of patent abstracts in the selected topics are present in Table 8. These probability distributions indicate how the different EU regions contribute to each individual topic, demonstrating

Table 1a. Weak signal keywords and related invention activities.

Weak signal keywords	Number of related patents
Accommodation , shuttering, camping	1098
Advertisement , commercial, advertise, webpage, publishing, prompting, friend, online, sms, choose, notify, renew, advertising	1606
Anticancer , cytotoxicity, metastasis, somatostatin, hepatitis, radionuclide, ceramide, pyrimidine, antitumor, quinazoline, apoptosis, macrophage, liposome, histocompatibility, rodent, immunology, carcinoma, alkanoyl, neovascularization, autoimmune, tautomer, arginine, choline, monocyte, mammalian, malignancy, reproducible, chemotherapy, death, fibrosis, administering, integrin, dystrophy, fertility, immunosuppression, mitochondrial, methionine, interferon, bioactivity, schizophrenia, cytoplasm, suffering, depolymerization, fever, arthritis, pancreas, mortality, mucosal, solvate, potency, prophylaxis, proliferation, hydrate, angiogenesis, fertilization, pathology, mimetic, therapeutic, sepsis, formyl, methoxy, lymphocyte, chimeric, phospholipase, segregating, phospholipid, piperidine, liver, tcell, hydrolase, diabete, tuberculosis, carboxy, brightener, thrombosis, prodrug, kidney, toxin, transplant, sclerosis, homology, osteoarthritis, fibroblast, marrow, cyclohexyl, defective, colon, tyrosine, atherosclerosis, metabolite, tumour, thiazole, polyphosphate, mononuclear, bowel, amyloid, ventricular, germ	10273
Biomass , gasification, refinery, bioreactor, fermentation, ethanol, pepper, grape, broth, nitrate, fossil, greenhouse, herb, silage, maize, wine	1851
Biosensor , analyte, biomolecule	1222
Cellphone	27
Cement , slump, clinker, rheology, copolymerisation, translucency, consolidation, alkalinity	1132
Cooking , cooker, stove, digester, utensil, blowoff, supercapacitor, recipe, pastry	1590
Construct , modularity	520
Education , inability, aviation, consultation, extrude, sharpener, online, intervene, avionic, demarcation, disaster, society, searching, ventricular	750

Table 1b. Weak signal keywords and related invention activities.

Weak signal keywords	Number of related patents
Flight , waypoint, airframe, airport, spanwise, refueling, avionic, tanker, craft	1969
Gaming , multiplayer, redemption, proceeding, outcome, online, distraction, voucher, friend, adoption, ranking	1039
Greenhouse , silage, stalk, harvest, borne, pepper, cultivation, vegetation, grape, fungi, farm, biomass, shredder, distillate, crop	2016
Health , Care, consultation, hospital, diet, linoleic, polyphenol	1810
Leisure , entertainment, online, aviation, playing	116
Media , renderer, playlist	573
Motorcycle , fender, windscreen, handgrip, headlight	920
Planet , gearing, sun, bogie	699
Sustainability , poise, hydrogenating, anisotropy, butene, cyclohexyl, cmin, overgrowth, carbonylation, borohydride, prescribed, durometer, sharpener, methoxy, govern, society, novolac, diblock, thiazole, shelving, displaceable, carboxymethyl, cumbersome combust, ventricular, electrovalve, brightener, screwing, red, recyclability, extrude, hydroxylamine, ignitability, discs, microfabrication, flammability, potting, thioester electrocatalyst, flocculating, protecting, lactide, polyisoprene, alkanoyl, envisage, bioactivity, copolymerisation, sparking, piperidine, varnish, stirring, ceramide, nitrate, saliency, counteracting, alkylphenol, volatilization, rodent, accretion, flaking, praseodymium choline, depolymerization, evaporate, oscillate, monoglyceride, citric, linoleic, diene, terpene onpress, brightening, granulometry, dimethyl, interpolate, coatability, gadolinium, sulfonate, polyamine, quinazoline, dyestuff, nanocomposite deformability alkalinity, bedplate vaporizing, polyphenol, chlorination, tautomer, pepper microdroplet, rutile, tetrachloride, calcination, sputtering, polyanion, cranking, thermoformable, pyrimidine, lipid, phospholipid, tampon, maize ferric, acetylene inject diamine dimerization, carboxy, atomizer, cytoplasm, arginine, avionic, radiant, phenylene, phospholipase, formability, aluminosilicate, somatostatin rosin amlodipine turbomachine, dipeptide, polyphosphate methionine, formyl	47525
Symptom , bowel, amelioration, sepsis, sclerosis, alleviation, schizophrenia, osteoarthritis, prophylaxis, administering, atherosclerosis, syndrome, arthritis, hyperactivity, dementia, antiobesity, alzheimer, inflammation, piperidine, mood, suffering, obesity, mellitus, deficit, analgesic, potency, pathology, abuse, hypertension, fever, endocrine, athlete, overgrowth, hyperglycemia, allergy, pain, amlodipine	3364
Vaccine , tuberculosis, vaccination, antigen, immunology, chicken, allergy, pathogen, hepatitis, chimeric, mammalian, tcell, histocompatibility, fertilization, replicating, rodent, epitope, hcv, therapeutic, lymphocyte, immunosuppression, interferon, mucosal, carcinoma, neovascularization, fertility, mimic, antitumor, depolymerization, pathology, cytoplasm, monocyte, inactivation, toxin	3042
Wine , grape, pepper, cappuccino, brewing, herb, pastry, coffee, fermentation, lactide, alkylphenol, apartment, broth, bedplate, drink, flour, biomass	1509

Table 2. Strong signal keywords and related invention activities.

Strong signal keywords	Number of related patents
Aircraft, turbine, vehicle, chassis	11955
Broadcast, multimedia, transmit, receptor, display, radio	10466
Cancer, peptide, tumor, medicament, antibody, pharmaceutical, nucleic, disease, molecule, therapy, precursor, amino, irradiation, drug, patient, virus, treatment, cell, membrane	51710
Lighting, dust, washing, tissue, luminance, security, encoding, tire, protein, storage, sensor	9907
Mobile	192409
Wind, emitting, plant	5294

Table 3. Forward citation (five year) and strong/weak signals, ANOVA analysis.

	sum_sq	DF	F	PR(>F)
C(strong_weak_signals)	2.083034e+03	1.0	46.616547	8.646175e-12
Residual	1.637193e+07	366390.0	NaN	NaN

Table 4. Forward citation (five year), average.

	forward citation (5 year)
Weak signal related patents	1.665
Strong signal related patents	1.486

Table 5. Breakthrough inventions (1% most cited patents) and strong/weak signals, ANOVA analysis.

	sum_sq	DF	F	PR(>F)
C(strong_weak_signals)	0.165795	1.0	20.504968	0.000006
Residual	2962.482775	366390.0	NaN	NaN

Table 6. Breakthrough inventions (1% most cited patents), average.

	Breakthrough inventions
Weak signal related patents	0.009
Strong signal related patents	0.007

how they are concentrating their invention activities on specific topics, reflecting R&D priorities. For example, the results show that Paris has the highest regional topic weights in water technologies (Topic 0) and protein acid (Topic 3), whereas München specialize in aircraft/vehicle power systems (Topic 6). Moreover, Hauts-de-Seine is strongly presented in the following invention activities such as cell domain/embodiment (Topic 1), image display (Topic 2), data systems (Topic 4) and sensor-based intelligence systems (Topic 5). By employing interdisciplinary elements of economic innovation, foresight and big data fields, the research linked technology foresight and regional innovation activities, as well as explored possibilities of identifying and assessing entrepreneurial discovery processes with weak and strong signals of technological changes.

Discussion and conclusion

This research presents a text mining approach to detect entrepreneurial discovery processes with weak/strong signals and explores the possibilities of incorporating technology foresight in the design and planning of European S3. The empirical study demonstrates how Big Data sets can be analysed in different European regions. Specifically, we analysed patent claim database and extracted weak/strong signals. We then utilised CorEx topic modelling to identify invention activities with weak and strong signals, as well as employ the ANOVA statistical method to examine whether patent values can be assessed by the weak and strong signals of technological development. In the final stage, an unsupervised text mining approach was used to map European patent activities related to weak/strong technology signals and compute regional topic weights. The results

Table 7. The top 10 ranked words of selected weak/strong signal related topics in patent activities.

Topic 0		Topic 2		Topic 4		Topic 6	
<i>Word</i>	<i>probability</i>	<i>word</i>	<i>probability</i>	<i>Word</i>	<i>probability</i>	<i>word</i>	<i>probability</i>
washing	0.031	portion	0.021	display	0.030	vehicle	0.071
method	0.021	display	0.020	information	0.021	tire	0.035
water	0.017	direction	0.016	Data	0.017	turbine	0.032
plant	0.016	surface	0.016	device	0.017	control	0.023
invention	0.015	first	0.015	First	0.015	wind	0.019
dust	0.015	body	0.013	method	0.013	system	0.018
present	0.011	side	0.011	security	0.012	aircraft	0.018
rubber	0.011	image	0.011	One	0.012	power	0.016
step	0.008	second	0.011	system	0.010	air	0.012
tub	0.007	position	0.011	Unit	0.010	unit	0.071
Topic 1		Topic 3		Topic 5			
<i>word</i>	<i>probability</i>	<i>word</i>	<i>probability</i>	<i>word</i>	<i>probability</i>		
cell	0.038	invention	0.031	signal	0.032		
base	0.031	protein	0.021	Light	0.021		
bead	0.019	present	0.017	Value	0.020		
channel	0.017	tissue	0.017	First	0.016		
shoulder	0.015	comprising	0.015	Unit	0.015		
block	0.014	relates	0.013	second	0.013		
domain	0.011	methods	0.012	sensor	0.012		
embodiments	0.010	acid	0.012	based	0.012		
include	0.010	said	0.010	detection	0.010		
may	0.009	proteins	0.010	Time	0.009		

Table 8. Regional topic weights in patent activities.

Region	Topic 0	Topic 1	Topic 2	Topic 3	Topic 4	Topic 5	Topic 6
Hauts-de-Seine	347.5	394.2	254.8	475,1	2894,1	701,1	137,7
Paris	414.4	259.1	147.8	2061,1	1449,3	376,5	132,1
München	346.1	143.1	224.4	688,5	983,5	449,6	467,3
Stockholm country	165.1	222.3	127.7	385,4	1216,4	288,2	168,7
South-East North Brabant	138.3	145.7	148.9	127,7	1002,5	620,3	353,6
Helsinki-Uusimaa	189.2	157.9	138.7	173,9	1312,2	272,2	115,7
Inner London West	217.6	79.6	177.1	344,2	754,5	188,3	200,3
Madrid	259.3	86.5	143.3	638,3	519,8	119,7	124,2

reveal in which areas different EU regions contribute and also reflect R&D priorities. The proposed approach can be used to envision future innovation ecosystems and study weak signal related invention activities across territories, as well as to calculate regional topic weights and develop policy road mapping for innovation ecosystem development in the EU.

In addition, this study shows that patents related to weak technology signals rather than strong, are more likely to be high-impact innovations and to serve as a basis for future technological developments, implying that weak signals matter for detecting breakthrough inventions. As the quantity of information is growing rapidly in today's digital economy, decision-makers often lack appropriate tools and methods to process massive amounts of external information, interpret signals of impeding technological changes and use them in strategic and innovation management. The proposed approach in this study can help policy-makers and companies to widen the ecosystem-foresight lens and to detect future technology threats and opportunities.

The analysis presented in the research can be replicated to examine relationship between weak/strong signals and start-up performance. Specifically, the research can be extended to identify start-up entrepreneurial activities across territories with technology weak and strong signals. As start-up entrepreneurs explore new market opportunities and bring into existence novel business models, they reshape markets and value networks across industries. Therefore, studying entrepreneurial

activities with weak signals can help firms and policymakers to anticipate where 'creative destruction' will unfold and in which business areas they should expect business discontinuities driven by new technologies and business models.

Data availability

Underlying data

Figshare: European patent data for text analytics <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.19130729.v2> (Bzhalava *et al.*, 2022a)

This project contains the following underlying data:

- EP_data_for_text_analytics.csv (European patent data combined with the OECD-REGPAT and OECD Patent Quality Indicators databases).

Extended data

Figshare: Extended data.docx

<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.19146494.v2> (Bzhalava *et al.*, 2022b)

This project contains the following extended data:

- Extended data.docx

Data are available under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license](#) (CC-BY 4.0).

Ethics and consent

Ethical approval and consent were not required.

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Version 1

Reviewer Report 19 May 2022

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Hugo Pinto

¹ Faculdade de Economia, Universidade do Algarve, Faro, Portugal

² Centro de Estudos Sociais, Universidade de Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

The article "Identifying entrepreneurial discovery processes with weak and strong technology signals: a text mining approach" is a relevant contribution to the literature on smart specialization. It is centered in the textual analysis of patent abstracts from 2000 to 2009 provided by EPO and uses a mining approach to collect technology weak and strong signals, linking these signals to invention activities for the period 2010–2018.

The article presents several good ideas. Nevertheless, I recommend some corrections for the consideration of authors.

- First, smart specialization is a process that is far from being centered in technological diversification. It is anchored in the development of domains where a specific region can excel for its structural change. These domains can be technological intensive or not. This standpoint means that the paper only addresses the entrepreneurial discovery processes that are highly connected with domains where patenting is key – usually more technological. Domains where DUI learning modes are dominant are neglected in this way. And they are crucial, especially in peripheral and/or lagging regions. This limitation should be discussed and referenced in the text.
- Secondly, being the text about the EDP, few lines are spent in clarifying the concept or giving evidence of the many (disparate) ways regions have tried to engage to actively direct the EDPs. Sometimes EDPs were directly related with findings using quantitative evidence-based approaches but were also inspired by participatory and qualitative approaches. A small summary of these practices can be presented to justify the pertinence and gap that this specific approach intends to solve.
- Thirdly, S3 is commonly referred to as a place-based strategy. There is room to accommodate a stronger regional focus in this article. In two ways. In a theoretical way, many contributions from the evolutionary geography of innovation, are directly aligned

with this approach, focusing patent portfolios, please cf. many recent contributions of Ron Boschma and co-authors and about relatedness. In the empirical way, the results (that are already presented) could emphasize this matter of regional smart specializations and regional diversification in EU.

- Finally, the option concerning the selection of periods is not clear. It deserves more justification.

Revise the word "cited".

Consolidate the decimals in the tables, in particular ANOVA.

Tables referring topics should be revised. Instead of "Topic 1, Topic ..." insert the full name of the Topics: (Topic 0), cell domain/embodiment (Topic 1), image display (Topic 2), protein acid (Topic 3), data systems (Topic 4), sensor-based intelligence systems (Topic 5) and aircraft/vehicle power systems (Topic 6).

Good luck!

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it engage with the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

Are all the source data and materials underlying the results available?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Regional Economics, Economic Geography, Specialist in Smart Specialisation, Quantitative Studies

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 30 May 2022

Levan Bzhalava, University of Turku, Turku, Finland

Dear Dr. Pinto,

We would like to thank you for the effort and expertise that you contributed towards reviewing the manuscript. We sincerely appreciate all your comments and suggestions, which are all valuable and very helpful for revising and improving the manuscript.

With best wishes,

Levan Bzhalava

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Author Response 12 Oct 2022

Levan Bzhalava, Tallinn University of Technology, Estonia

We would like to thank the reviewer for constructive comments and suggestions, which helped us considerably to improve the manuscript. Below we provide responses to the reviewer's comments:

- First, smart specialization is a process that is far from being centered in technological diversification. It is anchored in the development of domains where a specific region can excel for its structural change. These domains can be technological intensive or not. This standpoint means that the paper only addresses the entrepreneurial discovery processes that are highly connected with domains where patenting is key – usually more technological. Domains where DUI learning modes are dominant are neglected in this way. And they are crucial, especially in peripheral and/or lagging regions. This limitation should be discussed and referenced in the text.

Author Response: We included discussion regarding limitations of the research in the Discussion and Conclusion section.

- Secondly, being the text about the EDP, few lines are spent in clarifying the concept or giving evidence of the many (disparate) ways regions have tried to engage to actively direct the EDPs. Sometimes EDPs were directly related with findings using quantitative evidence-based approaches but were also inspired by participatory and qualitative approaches. A small summary of these practices can be presented to justify the pertinence and gap that this specific approach intends to solve.
- Thirdly, S3 is commonly referred to as a place-based strategy. There is room to accommodate a stronger regional focus in this article. In two ways. In a theoretical way, many contributions from the evolutionary geography of innovation, are directly aligned with this approach, focusing patent portfolios, please cf. many recent contributions of Ron Boschma and co-authors and about relatedness. In the empirical way, the results (that are already presented) could emphasize this matter of regional smart specializations and regional diversification in EU.

Author Response: We extended the literature review and provided more in-depth discussion regarding entrepreneurial discovery processes (EDPs) and a place-based innovation strategy as

well as presented quantitative and qualitative approaches concerning many different ways regions have tried to engage to actively direct EDPs (please see the Conceptual Framework section)

- Finally, the option concerning the selection of periods is not clear. It deserves more justification.

Author Response: We included an explanation regarding the selection of periods.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 04 May 2022

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.15652.r28962>

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Muhammad Ali

Friedrich Schiller University, Jena, Germany

I had the pleasure of reading this paper. It is a very nicely done work with a potentially significant impact on policy. Following are my comments:

1. The authors present a novel approach to predicting signals. In order to show that their methodology is better or more sophisticated, the authors should explain how their methodology is different from the existing methodologies.
2. In the methodology section, the authors write that they merge two REGPAT databases by the address of the authors. Since one of the indicators measures the impact of patents after a lag of a few years, I wonder if the addresses in the two databases are kept the same at the point of publication or if they update it later? If the latter is true, then how did the authors account for the cases where authors changed their address?
3. I guess there are typos in Equations 1 and 2. “NNij” should be “NNj”.
4. It is not clear to me how the term “tw” is used. If it is kept fixed at 0.05 then what purpose does it serve? My guess is that the value of “tw” is conditional on the time elapsed since publication. Whatever the case might be, it needs better clarification.
5. For those who are new to text mining, it would be helpful to know how the authors dealt with synonyms. For instance, “playing”, “lighting”, etc. can have several meanings when used as keywords. How did the authors ensure that they selected the correct patents?
6. How can weak signals be more likely to transform into high-impact innovations? Authors need to explain it better and relate it with theory. It can be done in the discussion section which is quite short.

7. Data is merged inside the methodology section. Either make a different section or rename this section as "Data and Methodology".
8. The theoretical section does not present an established theory. I would instead rename it as "Conceptual Framework".
9. I really appreciate the depth in the analysis of this paper. However, since this tool is for policymakers, I wonder if it is feasible for the policymakers to merge so many datasets and do all these steps every time they sit for a policy meeting?

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it engage with the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

Are all the source data and materials underlying the results available?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Economics of innovation, national system of innovation

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 30 May 2022

Levan Bzhalava, University of Turku, Turku, Finland

Dear Dr. Ali,

We would like to thank you for taking the necessary time and effort to review the manuscript.

We sincerely appreciate all your valuable comments and suggestions, which will help us to

improve the quality of the manuscript.

With best wishes,

Levan Bzhalava

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Author Response 12 Oct 2022

Levan Bzhalava, Tallinn University of Technology, Estonia

We would like to thank the reviewer for constructive comments and suggestions, which helped us considerably to improve the manuscript. Below we provide responses to the reviewer's comments:

- The authors present a novel approach to predicting signals. In order to show that their methodology is better or more sophisticated, the authors should explain how their methodology is different from the existing methodologies.

Author Response: We included a more substantiate explanation of how the methodology proposed in the research is different from the previous ones.

- In the methodology section, the authors write that they merge two REGPAT databases by the address of the authors. Since one of the indicators measures the impact of patents after a lag of a few years, I wonder if the addresses in the two databases are kept the same at the point of publication or if they update it later? If the latter is true, then how did the authors account for the cases where authors changed their address?

Author Response: Addresses of patents are defined by OECD. We just matched OECD patent data and European Patent full text database. We made no changes or updates to addresses of patents.

- It is not clear to me how the term "tw" is used. If it is kept fixed at 0.05 then what purpose does it serve? My guess is that the value of "tw" is conditional on the time elapsed since publication. Whatever the case might be, it needs better clarification.

Author Response: Terms associated with weak signal topics usually have a low absolute occurrence frequency and a high time-weighted increasing rates. On the contrary, terms related to strong signal topics are likely to have a high absolute occurrence frequency and a high time-weighted increasing rates. In line with Yoon (2012), we study the occurrence of keywords and uses a time-weighted method (combination of time weights (tw), total number of periods (n) and specific period (j) in which term frequencies are counted) to put recent appearances of keywords more important than past appearances. For instance, in this part of formula: $1 - tw \times (n - j)$, lets calculate: $1 - 0.05 \times (10 - 1) = 1 - 0.05 \times (9) = 1 - 0.45 = 0.55$ $1 - 0.05 \times (10 - 2) = 1 - 0.05 \times (8) = 1 - 0.4 = 0.6$... $1 - 0.05 \times (10 - 10) = 1 - 0.05 \times (0) = 1$

- I guess there are typos in Equations 1 and 2. "NNij" should be "NNj".

Author Response: Yes, there were typos in Equations 1 and 2. We corrected them. Thank you for pointing it out.

- For those who are new to text mining, it would be helpful to know how the authors dealt with synonyms. For instance, "playing", "lighting", etc. can have several meanings when used as keywords. How did the authors ensure that they selected the correct patents?

Author Response: Previous research on text mining suggests that synonym replacement on a one-to-one word level is very likely to produce errors. We first extract only noun and adjective keywords as they represent technology concepts, and then use word2vec algorithm to group weak signal keywords. Afterward, the manual selection is used to group synonymous and to pick up main keywords associated with different sectors. After grouping weak and strong signal keywords, we use them as anchor words and utilize Correlation Explanation (CorEx) topic modelling to identify related invention activities across EU regions for the period 2010-2018.

- How can weak signals be more likely to transform into high-impact innovations?
Authors need to explain it better and relate it with theory.

Author Response: We included a more substantiate explanation of how the weak signals are more likely to transform into high-impact innovations.

- Data is merged inside the methodology section. Either make a different section or rename this section as "Data and Methodology".

Author Response: We renamed the section as "Data and Methodology".

- The theoretical section does not present an established theory. I would instead rename it as "Conceptual Framework".

Author Response: We renamed it as "Conceptual Framework" and also extended literature review.

- I really appreciate the depth in the analysis of this paper. However, since this tool is for policymakers, I wonder if it is feasible for the policymakers to merge so many datasets and do all these steps every time they sit for a policy meeting?

Author Response: Once data analyses are done and Python programming codes are written, most of the parts can be automated so that policymakers to have automated knowledge management tools.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.
